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A 360-VR AUTHORING TOOL FOR ENGINEERING TEACHERS

PREPARING VIRTUAL EXCURSIONS FOR MINING ENGINEERING EDUCATION COURSES

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ABSTRACT

Fitting an excursion into a lecture plan has been always a challenge to organize [1] [2] [3] [4] – even before the global pandemic outbreak. Mixed Reality (MR) media enables teachers to invite students virtually into a remote location for a few minutes during the lecture. It enables explaining key aspects of a process or a machine in detail and finally supports aligning the practical insight with the theoretical concepts behind it. Previous publications have proofed the benefits of including MR into a teaching curricular [1] [5] [6] [7] [8]. However, the available prototypes tend to cover unique cases and barely enable teachers to adjust content to their specific needs.

This shift from on-site to virtual excursions calls for new MR authoring tools and digital skills for teachers. Aligned with the teacher 4.0 concept [9], the development of an authoring tool in context of mining engineering education is currently realized and will be presented in this paper. The tool is developed within the project MiReBooks that is funded by the EIT Raw Materials initiative.

In this paper, we introduce the concept, design and development of an authoring tool to support teachers preparing virtual excursions based on 360° video imagery. In addition to the specification of the technical design, the paper outlines the initial results of the evaluation, which is conducted in cooperation with mining engineering teachers throughout Europe. We will conclude with an outlook on follow-up development steps.

1 INTRODUCTION

Authoring tools enable teachers to prepare content themselves without programming skills [10]. Thereby, they address the current increasing need for Mixed Reality (MR) based teaching content. In terms of virtual excursions, this means that teachers would not only prepare the typical content slides for their lecture, but also add content (i.e. VR-media slides) for a short excursion into a virtual mine site on their PCs as part of their lecture preparation. Mining engineering teachers need to teach in-depth knowledge in exploration, extraction, conveying and the processing of raw materials. Often the environment influences the design of a bucket wheel excavator heavily. Conveying a better understanding of mining machines through 360° videos, would allow teachers to emphasize the understanding of processes in mining engineering more hands-on.

The current integration of MR -based classes still requires good programming skills from teachers and thus makes virtual excursions preparation not easily applicable for everyone [7]. The use cases, along with the challenges, have been previously addressed in the teacher 4.0 concept of Abdelrazeq et al. [9]. As notable in some of the previous works, the integration of MR into the class requires a close examination of didactical planning, technological skills and possible requirements from an organization standpoint [11].

User centered design (UCD) methods and agile design principles support the development and design of the authoring tool. Those methods had been applied in this research project as they can minimize the needed technical skill level for the preparation of MR based lectures. UCD is an iterative approach in software development in order to develop concepts, designs and prototypes that can be understood fast and is easily accepted by users [12]. Methods such as focus group interviews, the development of user stories as well as usability tests support better understanding of the requirements from software [13] [14].

In order to contribute into MR authoring tool concepts in education, we will first describe the aim of the MiReBooks Project and the role of an authoring tool for the teaching 4.0 concept. The following sections will introduce the main three guiding research questions for developing the authoring tool concept. First, the question regarding learning objectives for virtual excursions and their implication for the tool development will be presented. Second, the question on the workflow of the authoring tool will be addressed with the method of user stories. Third, self-explanatory software design will be applied in order to minimize the need for additional competences for the teachers. Finally, the conclusion will provide the next steps and further fields to test the authoring tool.

2 THE 360-VR AUTHORING TOOL

The aim of the MiReBooks Project is to enhance classical mining engineering teaching concepts with MR technology. As future mining engineers will need to balance more complex mining equipment with additional sustainable demands, the understanding of the actual environment through 360° videos becomes a key focus for current teachers.

As the contemporary 2D teaching material lacks hands-on experience from a mine site, the development of MR content such as 3D models and 360° videos are produced throughout Europe [11]. Thereby providing a textbook enhanced with MR content for teaching. Moreover, the project enables the research on teaching 4.0 skills in the context with MR based classes [1], [5], [6], [7], [11].

In addition to the technological development and infrastructure, a vital part of the MiReBooks project is to enable mining engineering teachers to plan and provide MR based lectures on their own. Therefore, the authoring tool is developed with UCD methods. The aim of this authoring tool is to support teachers with an intuitive software to prepare their own MR based lectures.

In order to define the requirements, the project-involved teachers were asked about their vision and expectations of MR in teaching. The result had been analyzed in the works of Daling et. al [5]. Learning objectives were defined with UCD methods such as contextual interviews that were carried out after testing MR in lectures. Thus, three questions arise, such as:

1. What is needed to support teachers in order to reach the learning goals of virtual excursions?
2. What kind of MR features have to be included in an authoring tool to meet the proposed learning goals?
3. How do the features need to be designed in order to be intuitively understood by teachers during their lecture preparation?

The authoring tool is developed with the Unity 3D game engine. Based on a previous requirement analysis and further iterative development, the authoring tool runs on PCs as teachers tend to prepare their lectures with this device. Hence, the Unity 3D game engine was adapted accordingly for the software development. In addition, due to the user stories method, it is optional whether teachers visit the mine in MR or navigate their students with a PC or tablet based function.

2.1 Authoring tool to support the Learning Goals for Virtual Excursions

The development of the concept required a close analysis of how teachers prepare for classes in general, how they perceive their role through the introduction of MR and how they assumed virtual excursions are supporting them in their learning objectives. Their ideas as well as the insight in lecture preparing and reflection of the test lectures supported the authoring tool concept. With contextual interviews, the teachers were asked to reflect the usefulness of different prepared MR technologies they tested with students in their lectures [5]. This first study gave a better understanding of the expectations of teachers wishing to include virtual excursions in their lecture.

As a next step, the collected use cases for teaching were sorted in two internal workshops and two additional interviews with mining engineering teachers to the learning taxonomy level of Bloom (see figure 1). The Bloom learning taxonomy addresses different level of learning, starting from higher to lower levels such as

evaluate, synthesize, apply, analyze, remember and understand [15]. The use case with the highest taxonomy level addresses synthesizing and would be an application where students create their own virtual scenarios with sandbox game elements. The use case enabling students to simulate blasting in MR lets them apply knowledge through placing mining equipment and simulating how the blast would theoretically be played out in a save VR environment. A training scenario that lets students search for security errors such as finding the errors in a prerecorded 360° video scene addresses the analysis taxonomy level. Those first listed use cases enable students to apply theoretical knowledge, but might not need a teacher directly involved in the interaction with the MR medium.

Figure 1: Aligned ideas for MR use cases in class with Blooms learning taxonomy levels.

The use cases of interacting or classifying 3D equipment as well 360° video tours in a prerecorded mining area would often need additional knowledge of the teacher to explain additional aspects. Therefore the lower taxonomy levels such as understanding and remembering require a closer communication between teacher and student during the lecture in order to ask questions and discuss [5]. Thus, those scenarios need to be highly flexible in their design in order to address the individual teaching style of teachers. Those use cases are more likely to be used in the lectures to support the interaction in class, while security trainings or blasting try-outs are better applicable without the lectures due to the extended time that is needed. Thus, the idea of virtual tours through the mine, 3D displays of mining equipment addresses learning goals of understanding and remembering.

To address the first question of what is needed to support teachers in order to reach the learning goals of virtual excursions, the teachers were interviewed by Daling et al. in order to extract the MR use cases in teaching. The authors analyzed that teachers wished to use 360° camera footage in order to visit mine sites virtually with their students during a lecture [5]. For those virtual excursions, the questioned teachers

wished to take place during class. This indicated that the learning goals, which the teachers wished to address during the virtual excursion, links to a lower taxonomy level (understand, remember).

The vital role of the teacher for the learning process in a virtual excursion calls for the design of an authoring tool instead of a finished developed MR experience. This allows the teacher to adjust the excursion at runtime and point the students attention towards specific aspects at the location. Additionally, those use cases addressing a higher learning taxonomy level are usually more complex to design and program. Due to the requirements of MR classes such as presented in the VRMine project [16], the support of software developers and game designers are needed. The transfer to an authoring tool for teachers with basic knowledge in game engines seems further challenging. The more detailed insight in learning goals of virtual excursions and their implication for the video production of 360° video content had been discussed by Khodaei et. al. previously [11].

2.2 Authoring tool Mixed Reality Features on the Basis of User Stories

For the second question on what features are needed to meet the proposed learning goals, three mining engineering teachers who are more familiar with MR were asked to describe their ideal workflow. In order to identify what teachers wish to include during classes and what they expect from the MR technology, the method of user stories was applied in one workshop. The workshop aim was to understand the needed features and unveil the expectation and skill level perceived by the teachers.

As authoring tools introduce a new workflow into the lecture preparation for teachers, it was needed to formulate user stories in order to understand the needed requirements and features. Those user stories were phrased in order to guide throughout the phases before lecture preparation, as well as during lecture and finally after the lecture. To formalize the user story, the teachers had a fixed structure consisting of a subject, an action with a certain content and a timeframe (see table 1).

Table 1. Formulation structure of a user story in order to understand what actions are relevant for the workflow.

Module	Meaning
As a <teacher> <student>	<who> should be enabled to do it
Verb + <imported content>	<action/interaction> that enables the user to do things with a <content>
<before> <during> <after>	<when> should the action take place

The following overview shows the results of the used technique by showing the requirements consisting of 10 user stories before the lecture, 8 user stories during the lecture and two after the lecture (see table 2). Those user stories were ranked in a next step into important and nice to have.

Table 2. user stories sorted by lecture preparation phase

Phase	User stories
Before lecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As a teacher I want to import my 360° images/videos from the mine into my lecture As a teacher I want to set certain view directions in my 360° videos before the lecture As a teacher I want to insert a break image into my 360° videos before my lecture As a teacher I want to know how long showing the 360° images takes before my lecture As a teacher I want to change and adapt my 360° videos/images before the lecture As a teacher I want to cut my 360° videos/images before the lecture As a teacher I want to place/insert text/annotations/images into my 360° videos/images before the lecture
During lecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As a teacher I want to switch between my 360° images/videos from the mine during my lecture As a teacher I want to switch between PowerPoint and 360° images during my lecture As a teacher I want to start and stop my 360° videos from the mine during my lecture As a teacher I want to track the time that shall be spent in 360° images during my lecture As a teacher I want to place/insert text/annotations/images into my 360° videos/images during the lecture As a teacher I want to know who is watching in what direction in my 360° videos during the lecture As a teacher I want to jump between certain view directions in my 360° videos during the lecture As a teacher I want to draw attention in my 360° images/videos during the lecture
After lecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As a teacher I want to save and restart at a certain time my 360° images/videos from the mine after my lecture As a teacher I want to share my 360° images/videos from the mine after my lecture

Based on the structural analysis of the user story, the following workflow for preparing the Learning Experience (LE) was conceptualized (see figure 2). LE refers to the resulting experience, the teachers wishes to convey. The tool concept consists of the phases, login and selection of different projects, preparing the lecture with self-recorded material and sharing the built LE with the class. Those steps resulted in the structure of a lobby, where the teacher selects the LE, a preparation step for the teacher to create the LE followed by a player module where students and teachers connect into one LE (see figure 2).

Figure 2: Overview on the three modules lobby, preparation and player.

Within the preparation phase, the following steps have been identified as important for the teacher in order to create the LE (see figure 3). The teacher needs to create the LE by opening and naming a project. Then, s/he need to load pre-stitched 360° videos into their project. Then assign their video material into slides and sort the slides into an order that fits the structure of the learning goal.

In addition, the action description in the user story give an insight in the needed features for the authoring tool development. Firstly, on each 360° video they set a viewing angle. The viewing angle defines where everyone entering the LE i tilted towards. Secondly, placing annotations on top of the 360° image such as texts, arrows and icons in order to highlight or explain certain points in the experience. Thirdly and finally being able to save the project into a LE format. Those features are needed to be predefined in the preparation phase by the teacher, as those were described in the user stories as part of the preparation process.

Figure 3. A detailed workflow on the steps that the teachers wished to do based on user development

2.3 Slides as key design element for MR based authoring tools

After the concept and features of the authoring tool is understood, the third question on how to design the features in an intuitive way are addressed. Thus, the first step is to make the interaction as intuitive and self-explanatory for teachers as possible in order to minimize the need for learning additional technical skills. The initial step aligns the design to familiar tools in order to apply the UCD principle of context understanding principles [17]. For part of the user story development, it is needed to understand what tools the teachers usually prepare their lectures with. As most of the teachers use tools like PowerPoint, the design elements of slides have been selected from PowerPoint both visually and terminologically.

The editor consists of three areas (see figure 4). The first and main area is a preview/working space area which takes 2/3 of the screen in the middle. The second

is a slide area that gives an overview of the selected video material on the bottom. The third is on the right side and allows to select tools and edit the size and color of text fields. This area is changing in regard whether the teacher is in editing or in playing mode. One key design decision to support the flexible and more floating switch between editing and playing is the factor, that the overview of the teacher is the same for editing and playing with regard to the overview area. Otherwise, a fundamental design change between preparation and teaching might cause confusion through the course and consequently neglecting the tool. In the area of the preview is a set of icons and annotation texts as well as the ability to select a starting angle. Apart from preparing annotations before the lecture, it is also possible to spontaneously add texts and arrows in play mode. The preparation and player mode were designed to have the similar preview and slides. The right side represents the needed tools for the editing or player more.

Figure 4. The overview of the authoring tool in preparation mode.

The first user interface study in may 2021 aimed to test how self-explanatory the used icons and concepts are. As the minig engineering teachers were already heavily involved in the design process, in this study seven students prepared the virtual excursion. In the selection of students a mix between male and female students is considered as well as different scientific fields and nationalities.

The study concept has a mixed approach of qualitative observation and a questionnaire with quantitative scales such as the System Usability Scale (SUS)[18]. The participant gets the authoring tool software along with 360° example videos. The participant is asked to perform a set of 12 tasks. The tasks are formulated along the workflow in figure 3. During the task completion the participant is asked to think aloud and is observed by both male and female developers and designers. Afterwards a questionnaire asks to reflect on how well they fulfilled each task.

The observation and questionnaire revealed that that the slide concept and preview field was intuitively understood. The SUS Score of 73,5 indicates that the usability of the tool is good, but there is still improvement for the tool needed. The qualitative

observation with the thinking aloud method revealed that the general impression of the tool feels overwhelming and the display of the duration of an annotation is not directly understood and the viewing angle concept was not grasped. Additionally, more features in the design of the text annotations (e.g. text alignments) were requested. Thus, additional further iterations and following a detailed study on the usability of the authoring tool are the next steps.

3 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In summary, we introduced the concept, design and development of an authoring tool to support teachers preparing virtual excursions based on 360° video imagery. Several steps in UCD methods such as contextual interviews, user stories and usability tests were applied through this process. Through the contextual interviews, it became clear that virtual excursions are mostly seen as a support during a lecture and thus would address learning goals that apply to lower taxonomy levels. Through the phrasing of user stories in workshops, the expectations towards an authoring tool and the steps in preparing the lecture were made visual for development. For minimizing the needed additional skills from the teacher, the tool design was built on software that is already used for lecture preparation such as Power Point. Moreover, the first User interface focused study indicate that the tool is intuitively designed and requires few prior knowledge in order to prepare a virtual excursion.

As next steps, additional user experience studies are needed and planned in order to further design the authoring tool into an intuitive support for preparing MR based lectures. Moreover, studies that analyze further interaction between teacher(s) and students during the virtual excursions are needed. Additional studies within other research fields such as construction sites, city planning or environmental classes would further support into creating more virtual excursions and testing best practices for MR based teaching.

In general, the development of supportive authoring software for teachers to prepare MR technologies continues to have great international relevance. Due to the growing need for new blended learning methods and the high variety of use cases further research applying the principles and methods of UCD support this current approach.

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Further references regarding the discussed project can be found under [MiReBooks.com](https://www.mirebooks.com).

REFERENCES

- [1.] Daling, L., Kommetter, C., Abdelrazeq, A., Ebner, M., Ebner, M., (2020), Mixed Reality Books: Applying Augmented and Virtual Reality in Mining Engineering Education. In: Geroimenko, V. (Ed.): Augmented reality in education. A new technology for teaching and learning. Cham: Springer (Springer Series on Cultural Computing), S. 185–195.
- [2.] DeWitt, J., Storksdieck, M. (2008), A Short Review of School Field Trips: Key Findings from the Past and Implications for the Future, *Visitor Studies*, Bd. 11, Nr. 2, 2008, S. 181–197.
- [3.] Boeve-de Pauw, J., van Hoof, J., van Petegem, P. (2019), Effective field trips in nature: the interplay between novelty and learning, *Journal of Biological Education*, Bd. 53, Nr. 1, 2019, S. 21–33.
- [4.] Behrendt, M., Franklin, T. „A Review of Research on School Field Trips and Their Value in Education.“ *International Journal of Environmental & Science Education International Journal of Environmental & Science*, Bd. 2014, Nr. 9, 2014, S. 235–245.
- [5.] Daling, L., Eck, C., Abdelrazeq, A., Hees, F. (2020): Potentials and Challenges of Using Mixed Reality in Mining Education. A Europe-Wide Interview Study. In: ACHI 2020: The Thirteenth International Conference on Advances in Computer-Human Interactions, S. 229–235.
- [6.] Suppes, R., Feldmann, Y., Abdelrazeq, A., Daling, L. (2019) Virtual reality mine: A vision for digitalized mining engineering education. Mining goes digital: Proceedings of the 39th international symposium 'Application of Computers and Operations Research in the Mineral Industry' (APCOM 2019), June 4-6, 2019, Wroclaw, Poland, hrsg. von Christoph Mueller, CRC Press, 2019, S. 17–24.
- [7.] Kalkofen, D, Mori, S, Ladinig, T, Daling, L, Abdelrazeq, A, Ebner, M, Ortega, M, Feiel, S, Gabl, S, Shepel, T, Tibbett, J, Laine, TH, Hitch, M, Drebenstedt, C & Moser, P 2020, Tools for Teaching Mining Students in Virtual Reality based on 360° Video Experiences. in Proceedings - 2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces, VRW 2020: Abstracts and Workshops (VRW), 9090430, Proceedings - 2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces, VRW 2020, Atlanta, GA, USA, pp. 455-459,
- [8.] McKenzie, S. , Rough, J., Spence, A., Patterson, N. (2019), Virtually There: The Potential, Process and Problems of Using 360° Video in the Classroom. In: IISIT 16, pp. 211–219. 2019.
- [9.] Abdelrazeq, A., Janßen, D., Tummel, C., Richert, A., Jeschke, S. (2016), Teacher 4.0: Requirements of the Teacher of the Future in Context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. ICERI 2016 Proceedings, 11/14/2016 - 11/16/2016, Seville, Spain, International Technology, Education and Development Conference hrsg. von Luis Gómez Chova et. al., IATED, 2016, S. 8221–8226. ICERI proceedings.
- [10.] Khademi, M., Haghshenas, M., Kabir, H. (2011): A Review On Authoring Tools. In: Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Distance Learning and Education, IPCSIT. pp. 40–44. IACSIT Press, Singapore (2011).
- [11.] Khodaei S.; Sieger, J.; Abdelrazeq, A.; Isenhardt, I. (2020): Learning Goals in 360° virtual excursion - media creation guideline for mixed-reality-based classes. In: ICERI 2020 Proceedings, S. 2552–2561.
- [12.] Sauro, J., Lewis, J., (2016): Quantifying the user experience: Practical statistics for user research. *Journal of Usability Studies*, Vol. 13, 3 (2018), 158–167 Morgan Kaufmann, 2016
- [13.] Baxter, K., Courage, C., Caine, K. (2015), *Understanding your users: A practical guide to user research methods*. Morgan Kaufmann, 2015.
- [14.] Cohn, M. (2010), *User Stories: für die agile Software-Entwicklung mit Scrum, XP u.a.*, mitp Verlag, Bonn 2010
- [15.] Bloom, B. S., Engelhart, M. D., Furst, E. J., Hill W. H., Krathwohl, D. R. (1956), *Taxonomy of educational objectives: the classification of educational goals, Handbook I: Cognitive domain*, New York: David McKay, 1956.
- [16.] Abdelrazeq, A, et al. (2019), A Virtual Reality Educational Tool in the Context of Mining Engineering - The Virtual Reality Mine. *INTED 2019 Proceedings*, 3/11/2019 - 3/13/2019, Valencia, Spain, 13th International Technology, Education and Development Conference hrsg. von Luis Gómez Chova et al., IATED, 2019, S. 8067–8073. INTED Proceedings.
- [17.] ISO 9241-210 (2010) ISO 9241-210. Ergonomics of Human-System Interaction-Part 210: Human-Centred Design For Interactive Systems. Génève: International Organization Standardization, 2010.
- [18.] Brooke, J. (1986), SUS: a "quick and dirty" usability scale". In P. W. Jordan; B. Thomas; B. A. Weerdmeester; A. L. McClelland (eds.). *Usability Evaluation in Industry*. London: Taylor and Francis.